

A first national-scale peatland drainage map, and improved mapping of peat erosion, for Scotland

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Release notes for policy and peatland managers

Version 1 - 29th of November 2024

What the data product is

This data product consists of Geographic information system (GIS) layers representing location and distribution of peatland degradation features (erosion and drainage) at a national scale in Scotland. These layers have been produced using Computer Vision Machine Learning (CVML) models trained to detect and segment these features in aerial imagery. The released data is available on the SEFARI Natural Asset Register Data Portal ([Peatland Drainage and Erosion Scotland](#)). It is comprised of 10 individual datasets, the predicted centrelines of individual drains, the predicted area of drains, the predicted drained area based on the 30-metre drainage buffer in the Peatland Code Field Guidance, the predicted area of erosion features, as well as the estimated density of each of these features at 10, 100, and 500 metre resolution. Examples of the released datasets are shown below.

What it is useful for

These new datasets may be useful for several groups of future users. The new estimates of drainage and erosion may help to improve national emissions estimates from peatlands in Scotland, if they were to be adopted as part of the formal UK level reporting of activity data in the National Atmospheric Emissions Inventory LULUCF sector. These improved estimates of peatland drainage and erosion may aid development of future peatland policy, via more precise peatland condition baseline or hotspot mapping. For example, the produced layers have already been used as components of an updated peatland condition map at 10 metre resolution which is in preparation to be published and is available as an [ArcGIS storymap](#). For peatland restoration project developers, these data products could potentially improve the cost estimates and feasibility of undertaking a project.

Important caveats and use notes

The released datasets are provided “as is” and as such there are a number of caveats to consider in their use.

- Due to time constraints, and the time intensive manual process involved, only a limited number of images (46 and 43 for drainage and erosion respectively) could be fully labelled to train the models. Whilst care was taken to ensure these images were representative of a range of seasons and spatial locations, this sparse set of training examples may result in better performance in some geographical areas than in others.
 - Additional survey data has been provided by Peatland ACTION and Forestry and Land Scotland, which may be incorporated to further refine the models on future releases (pending funding).
- A metadata layer which includes the imaging year for each image used to generate these outputs is available on request and may be made available in later releases if this dataset is updated.
- This may be used to explain degradation features derived from older imagery where there has since been restoration, or where construction has taken place e.g., onshore wind generation.
- In validating the model outputs (as described in the [published paper](#)), the predicted national extent of both eroded and drained peat is consistent within 12 percentage points of the UK GHG Inventory estimates. Additionally, the product exhibits good correlation with existing, site-based, survey datasets in the Flow Country and Cairngorms National Park which further validate the approach.
 - Both comparisons, however, highlight areas of disagreement between these datasets and the produced layers, discussed further in the [published paper](#).
- For full usage notes, please refer to the README file included in each of the downloadable datasets on the [Data portal](#).

Contacts for further queries or feedback on this product

The underlying imagery used to train the CVML models and perform nationwide inference is property of Bluesky Inc. and Getmapping Plc. and cannot be shared openly. For annotated examples, model training evaluation, external validation, and results, please refer to the [published paper](#). Further queries can be directed to Fraser Macfarlane (fraser.macfarlane@hutton.ac.uk). In particular, sources of additional field or desk-based surveys are of interest in case of future further validation and continuous improvement of the released product (pending funding).

Acknowledgments/Funding Sources

This work was supported by RESAS (the Scottish Government's Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services Division) as part of the Strategic Research programme 2022-27 as part of grants JHI-D3-2, JHI-C3-1, and JHI-D5-2. RESAS had no role in the study design, data analysis or reporting of this work.

Additionally, computing resources were made available by the Research Computing team at The James Hutton Institute through use of the "UK's Crop Diversity Bioinformatics HPC", Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BBSRC) Advanced Life Sciences Research Technology Initiative (ALERT) grants BB/S019669/1 and BB/X019683/1, and The Department of Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy Public Sector Research Establishment Infrastructure Fund.

Data Product Examples

The below figures give examples of the produced datasets.

In both the maps of drainage and erosion:

- top left - the per-unit area density of degradation at 500 metre resolution (i.e., each pixel in the image represents the fraction of ground covered in degraded peat attributable to each of the modelled degradation features)
- top right shows the same at 100 metre resolution
- bottom left shows the same at 10 metre resolution
- bottom right shows the vector layers overlaid on APGB aerial imagery.
 - Drainage: drain centrelines and drained area polygons
 - Erosion: eroding/bare peat polygons.

The final image shows the temporal and spatial distribution of imagery used to produce these data products.

Aerial images per year

